

WORKSHOP TATA KELOLA DAN STANDARISASI JOURNAL ONLINE STANDAR AKREDITASI NASIONAL

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approach for externalization of expert tacit knowledge
Apostolos Mishkin, Frederic Serletis

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RJI Maluku,
08 Agustus 2019

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(*Editor in chief EST UNM*)

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Editor In Chief

Journal of Educational Science and
Technology (EST) UNM

MANAGING EDITOR JPPK BK UNM

(<http://ojs.unm.ac.id/index.php/JPPK>)

**TIM AHLI RELAWAN JURNAL INDONESIA (RJI)
KD SULAWESI SELATAN**

(<http://www.jurnalindonesia.org/>)

TIM Jurnal UNM

TIM Jurnal BK Indonesia

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Reviewer Jurnal Nasional & Internasional bidang BK

KEBIJAKAN DAN STRATEGI TATA KELOLA JURNAL ONLINE STANDAR AKREDITASI

MUH. ILHAM BAKHTIAR, S.Pd.M.Pd

Editor In Chief

***Journal of Educational Science and
Technology (EST) UNM***

HP. 085299898201

MATERI

- **MANAJEMEN TATAKELOLA
(STRATEGI PENGELOLAAN JURNAL ONLINE
STANDAR AKREDITASI NASIONAL,
MANAJEMEN SETUP OJS, SETTING,
PLUGIN/SITEBAR**
- **MANAJEMEN PENERBITAN STANDAR
AKREDITASI**

Mengapa Harus Publikasi Jurnal ONLINE?????

1. Surat Dirjen Dikti No. 152/E/T/2012 : Wajib Publikasi Ilmiah Bagi S1/S2/S3
2. Undang-Undang Nomor 12 Tahun 2012 tentang Pendidikan Tinggi pasal 46 (2) bahwa hasil penelitian wajib disebarluaskan dengan cara diseminarkan, dipublikasikan, dan/atau dipatenkan oleh Perguruan Tinggi.
3. Peraturan Menteri Agama Republik Indonesia Nomor 55 Tahun 2014 ttng Peneltian dan Pengabdian pada masyarakat Psl 7 & 14: PT memfasilitasi penerbitan & Publikasi hasil penelitian dlam bentuk jurna ilmiah-ejournal
4. Peraturan Direktur Jenderal Dikti Nomor 1 Tahun 2014 tentang Pedoman Akreditasi Terbitan Berkala Ilmiah>> *Jenis Elektronik*
5. surat edaran Dirjen Penguatan Riset dan Pengembangan Kemenristekdikti Nomor: 193/E/SE/XII/2015 tentang akreditasi jurnal ilmiah secara elektronik.
6. **EDARAN dirjen dikti 1 April 2016 tentang jurnal online**
7. Kenaikan pangkat bagi pegawai negeri sipil (PAK) artikel memiliki akses online
8. Surat edaran dikti No:444/B/SE/2016 terkait “Implementasi SN dikti pada program magister, doktor dan doktor terapan
9. Surat Edaran Dikti No: 020/E5.2/SE/2017 ttng Akreditasi TBI Elektronik 2017
10. Permenristekdikti No 20 Tahun 2017 tunjangan LK dan GB
11. Luaran/tagihan Riset :
12. Permenristekdikti Nomor 9 Tahun 2018 Tentang Akreditasi Jurnal Ilmiah: Memiliki e-issn/issn online
13. Surat Permenristekdikti No: B/565/B.B1/HK.01.01/2019 tentang Sarana Wahana publikasi Ilmiah

Perbedaan

Instrumen Akreditasi TBI

Instrumen	Lama	Baru
Format/Media Jurnal	Format Cetak Wajib, On-line optional	Format On-line Wajib, Cetak optional
Manajemen Pengelolaan Terbitan	Berbasis cetak dikelola secara manual	E-Publishing System, dan mempersyaratkan pengelolaan secara full online (paperless)
Petunjuk Penulisan Bagi Penulis	Belum mempersyaratkan penggunaan template penulisan naskah	mempersyaratkan penggunaan template penulisan naskah untuk mempercepat pengelolaan naskah
Pengacuan , Pengutipan dan Penyusunan Daftar Pustaka	Konsisten secara manual	mempersyaratkan penggunaan aplikasi referensi
Manajemen Pengelolaan (Review)	Penekanan Pada Hasil	Penekanan pada Proses
Alamat Unik artikel	Tidak Ada	Mempersyaratkan memiliki identitas unik artikel (DOI)
Indeks Tiap Jilid	Manual	Otomatis dengan E-Publishing System
Penyebarluasan dan Dampak Ilmiah	Berbasis Oplah dan Tiras Penyebaran terbatas	Berbasis Akses dan Statistik penyebaran luas (global) dengan kunjungan unik
Indeksasi dan Internasionalisasi	Sulit dilaksanakan	Lebih mudah dilaksanakan

Perubahan Paradigma Tatakelola Terbitan Berkala Ilmiah

Media Cetak

Media Elektronik

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PROJECT

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search

Search

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tools

- What links here

page discussion view source history

OJS: Indonesian (id ID)

Contact:

- Lukman, S.T., M. Hum, Indonesian OJS Project Manager, Center for Scientific Documentation and Information, Indonesian Institute of Sciences, Jl. Gatot Subroto No. 10 Jakarta. E-mail: Ikmm_pdiilipi 'at' yahoo.com
- Ratih Keumala Sari, ratihkeumalasari@yahoo.co.id
- Swistien Kustantyana, swistien@gmail.com
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- Al Hafiz Akbar Maulana, alha002@gmail.com
- Ekawati Marlina, ekawati.marlina@lipi.go.id
- Rishadi, rishadi007@gmail.com

Paradigma Lama Akreditasi Cetak

A screenshot of the Arjuna National Journal Accreditation website. The header features the Arjuna logo and the text "AKREDITASI JURNAL NASIONAL". Below the header, there are navigation links for "Berita & Pengumuman", "Tentang Akreditasi", "Kontak", and a "Login" button. The main content area displays several articles with titles like "INSENTIF JURNAL YANG MEMENUHI STANDAR MUTU DAN TATA KELOLA NASIONAL TAHUN 2018" and "AKREDITASI". The interface is modern and uses a dark theme with blue and white accents.

Paradigma Baru Akreditasi elektronik
<http://arjuna2.ristekdikti.go.id/>

Manajemen Pengelolaan Jurnal Online

Electronic Publishing using OJS

Manajemen
Situs

IT Support /
web admin

Manajemen
Journal

Journal
Manager

Manajemen
Penerbitan

Editor

Section Editor

Reviewer

Copy Editor

Layout Editor

Proofreader

Peran dan Fungsi Pengguna OJS

Administrator

- tampilan, konfigurasi situs

Manajemen Jurnal

- konfigurasi jurnal

Editor

- proses review.

Editor Bagian

- menentukan reviewer, kesesuaian bidang ilmu naskah

Reviewer

- review naskah, rekomendasi

Copy Editor

- tata bahasa

Editor Layout

- tata letak, galley naskah

Proofreader

- finalisasi naskah

Penulis

- submit naskah, revisi

Pembaca

- membaca, mengunduh

Persyaratan Jurnal Ilmiah

- a. memuat artikel yang secara nyata memajukan ilmu pengetahuan, teknologi, dan/atau seni yang didasarkan pada hasil penelitian, perekayasaan, dan/atau telaahan yang mengandung temuan dan/atau pemikiran yang orisinal serta tidak plagiat;
- b. memiliki dewan penyunting jurnal berkualifikasi sesuai dengan bidang ilmu yang mewakili bidang ilmu pengetahuan, teknologi, dan/atau seni;
- c. melibatkan mitra bestari berkualifikasi sesuai dengan bidang ilmu jurnal dari berbagai perguruan tinggi dan/atau badan penelitian dan pengembangan serta industri yang berbeda dari dalam dan/atau luar negeri yang menyaring naskah secara objektif;
- d. menggunakan Bahasa Indonesia dan/atau bahasa resmi Perserikatan Bangsa-Bangsa;
- e. menjaga konsistensi gaya penulisan dan format penampilan;
- f. dikelola dan diterbitkan secara elektronik melalui jejaring teknologi informasi dan komunikasi;
- g. terbit sesuai dengan jadwal; dan
- h. memiliki nomor seri standar internasional secara elektronik (*Electronic International Standard Serial Number/EISSN*) dan pengenal objek digital (*Digital Object Identifier/DOI*).

(Peraturan Menteri Riset Teknologi dan Pendidikan Tinggi Nomor 9 Tahun 2018 Tentang Akreditasi Jurnal Ilmiah)

Permenristekdikti Nomor 20 Tahun 2017

Kriteria Jurnal Nasional

- a. Karya ilmiah ditulis dengan memenuhi kaidah ilmiah dan etika keilmuan;
- b. Memiliki ISSN;
- c. Memiliki terbitan versi online;
- d. Bertujuan menampung/mengomunikasikan hasil-hasil penelitian ilmiah dan/atau konsep ilmiah dalam disiplin ilmu tertentu;
- e. Ditujukan kepada masyarakat ilmiah/peneliti yang mempunyai disiplin-disiplin keilmuan yang relevan;
- f. Diterbitkan oleh Penerbit/ Badan Ilmiah/ Organisasi Profesi/Organisasi Keilmuan/ Perguruan Tinggi dengan unit-unitnya;
- g. Bahasa yang digunakan adalah Bahasa Indonesia dan/atau Bahasa Inggris dengan abstrak dalam Bahasa Indonesia dan/atau Bahasa Inggris;
- h. Memuat karya ilmiah dari penulis yang berasal dari minimal 2 (dua) institusi yang berbeda; dan
- i. Mempunyai dewan redaksi/editor yang terdiri dari para ahli dalam bidangnya dan berasal dari minimal 2 (dua) institusi yang berbeda.

Jurnal Nasional Terakreditasi adalah Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional yang diakreditasi oleh Kementerian.

Permenristekdikti Nomor 20 Tahun 2017

Kriteria Jurnal Internasional

- a. Karya ilmiah ditulis dengan memenuhi kaidah ilmiah dan etika keilmuan;
- b. Memiliki ISSN;
- c. Ditulis dengan menggunakan bahasa resmi PBB (Arab, Inggris, Perancis, Rusia, Spanyol, dan Tiongkok);
- d. Memiliki terbitan versi online;
- e. Dewan Redaksi (Editorial Board) adalah pakar di bidangnya paling sedikit berasal dari 4 (empat) negara;
- f. Artikel ilmiah yang diterbitkan dalam 1 (satu) nomor terbitan paling sedikit penulisnya berasal dari 2 (dua) negara;
- g. Jurnal yang diakui sebagai jurnal internasional oleh Direktorat Jenderal Sumber Daya Ilmu Pengetahuan, Teknologi, dan Pendidikan Tinggi
- h. Jurnal yang memenuhi kriteria pada huruf a sampai g, namun mempunyai faktor dampak 0 atau not available dari ISI Web of Science atau jurnal terindeks di SCImago dengan Q4 atau terindeks di Microsoft Academic Search
- i. Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional terakreditasi B dari Kementerian yang diterbitkan dalam salah satu bahasa PBB, terindeks di DOAJ dengan indikator green thick
- j. Karya Ilmiah pada prosiding internasional yang terindeks basis data internasional (Web of Science, Scopus) dinilai sama dengan jurnal internasional

Permenristekdikti Nomor 20 Tahun 2017

Kriteria Jurnal Internasional Bereputasi

Memenuhi kriteria jurnal internasional (slide sebelumnya) dengan indikator:

- a. Diterbitkan oleh asosiasi profesi ternama di dunia atau Perguruan Tinggi atau Penerbit (Publisher) kredibel;
- b. Terindeks oleh pemeringkat internasional yang diakui oleh Kementerian (contoh Web of Science dan/atau Scopus) serta mempunyai faktor dampak lebih besar dari 0 dari ISI Web of Science atau mempunyai faktor dampak (SJR) dari SCImago paling rendah Q3;
- c. Alamat jurnal dapat ditelusuri daring;
- d. Editor Boards dari Jurnal dapat ditelusuri daring dan tidak ada perbedaan antara editor yang tercantum di edisi cetak dan edisi daring;
- e. Proses review dilakukan dengan baik dan benar;
- f. Jumlah artikel setiap penerbitan adalah wajar dan format tampilan setiap terbitan tidak berubah ubah;
- g. Tidak pernah diketemukan sebagai jurnal yang tidak bereputasi atau jurnal meragukan oleh Direktorat Jenderal Sumber Daya Ilmu Pengetahuan, Teknologi, dan Pendidikan Tinggi; dan
- h. Jurnal Ilmiah Nasional terakreditasi A dari Kementerian yang diterbitkan dalam salah satu bahasa PBB, terindeks di DOAJ dengan indikator green thick

Persyaratan Pengajuan Akreditasi Jurnal Ilmiah

1. Memiliki nomor seri standar internasional secara elektronik (*Electronic International Standard Serial Number/EISSN*). Nama jurnal harus sesuai dengan yang terdaftar di issn.lipi.go.id.
2. Memiliki pengenal objek digital (*Digital Object Identifier/DOI*).
3. Mencantumkan persyaratan etika publikasi (*publication ethics statement*) dalam laman jurnal.
4. Jurnal ilmiah harus bersifat ilmiah, artinya memuat artikel yang secara nyata memajukan ilmu pengetahuan, teknologi, dan/atau seni yang didasarkan pada hasil penelitian, perekayasaan, dan/atau telaahan yang mengandung temuan dan/atau pemikiran yang orisinil serta tidak plagiat.
5. Jurnal ilmiah telah terbit paling sedikit 2 tahun berurutan, terhitung mundur mulai tanggal atau bulan pengajuan akreditasi.
6. Frekuensi penerbitan jurnal ilmiah paling sedikit 2 kali dalam satu tahun secara teratur.
7. Jumlah artikel setiap terbit sekurang-kurangnya 5 artikel, kecuali jika jurnal yang hanya memuat artikel *review* bidang ilmu tertentu

Unsur dan Bobot Penilaian

Unsur	Bobot	
	Manajemen	Substansi*
Penamaan Jurnal Ilmiah	3	-
Kelembagaan Penerbit	4	-
Penyuntingan dan Manajemen Jurnal	17	-
Substansi Artikel	-	39
Gaya Penulisan	-	12
Penampilan	8	-
Keberkalaan	6	-
Penyebarluasan	11	-
Jumlah	49	51

Suatu jurnal ilmiah dinyatakan terakreditasi Peringkat 2 apabila sekurang-kurangnya memperoleh nilai total 70 (manajemen dan substansi), dengan nilai substansi sekurang-kurangnya 26.

Disinsentif (maksimum -20) diberlakukan bila terjadi penyimpangan unsur-unsur **plagiasi** oleh sebuah jurnal ilmiah

Peringkat Akreditasi

Hasil Akreditasi Jurnal ilmiah yang ditetapkan Tim Akreditasi digunakan oleh Tim Penilai Angka Kredit (Tim PAK) Jabatan Fungsional untuk penilaian substansi artikel

STRATEGI PENGELOLAAN JURNAL ONLINE

Indikator	Nilai
Spesifik sehingga mencerminkan super spesialisasi atau spesialisasi disiplin ilmu tertentu	3
Cukup spesifik tetapi meluas mencakup bidang ilmu	2
Kurang spesifik dan bersifat umum	1
Tidak spesifik dan/atau memakai nama lembaga/lokasi lokal	0

Penamaan terbitan

Penamaan di website, metadata, dan galley harus sama dengan database ISSN

PENAMAAN

Terbitan Berkala Ilmiah

	Indikator	Nilai	Contoh 1	Contoh 2	Contoh 3
a	Spesifik sehingga mencerminkan superspesialisasi atau spesialisasi disiplin ilmu tertentu	3	COUNSELING Journal	Jurnal Plastik Rekonstruksi	Musikologi: Jurnal Penciptaan dan Pengkajian
b	Cukup spesifik tetapi meluas mencakup bidang ilmu	2	Mechatronics, Electrical Power, and Vehicular Technology	Keteknikan Pertanian	Journal Sensi: Strategic of Education in Information System
c	Kurang spesifik dan bersifat umum	1	Medical Journal of Indonesia	International Journal of Technology	Pharmaciana: Jurnal Kefarmasian
d	Tidak spesifik dan/atau memakai nama lembaga/lokasi lokal	0	Jurnal Pendidikan PGRI Kota Makassar	Tunas Siliwangi : Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Guru PAUD STKIP Siliwangi Bandung	Jurnal Kesehatan : Jurnal kesehatan dan kebidanan STIKES Gorongtalo

e-ISSN

- ▶ eISSN = pISSN
- ▶ Cek ke PDII LIPI <http://issn.pdii.lipi.go.id> atau di portal ISSN <https://portal.issn.org>
- ▶ Tampilkan di homepage

Lembaga Ilmu Pengetahuan Indonesia
Pusat Dokumentasi dan Informasi Ilmiah
LIPI Indonesian Institute of Sciences Center for Scientific Documentation and Information

Minggu, 29 April 2018

» ISSN ONLINE «

Pusat Dokumentasi dan Informasi Ilmiah (PDII) LIPI memiliki tugas dan wewenang untuk melakukan pemantauan atas seluruh publikasi terbitan berkala yang diterbitkan di Indonesia. Sebagai bagian dari tanggung-jawab tersebut, PDII menerbitkan ISSN (*International Standard of Serial Number*) yang merupakan tanda pengenal unik setiap terbitan berkala yang berlaku global.

ISSN diberikan oleh ISDS (*International Serial Data System*) yang berkedudukan di Paris, Perancis. ISSN diadopsi sebagai implementasi ISO-3297 di tahun 1975 oleh Subkomite no. 9 dari Komite Teknik no. 46 dari ISO (TC 46/SC 9). ISDS mendelegasikan pemberian ISSN baik secara regional maupun nasional. Untuk regional Asia dipusatkan di *Thai National Library*, Bangkok, Thailand. PDII LIPI merupakan satu-satunya *ISSN National Centre* untuk Indonesia.

» TERBITAN TERBARU «

Tarlim .
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ISSN 2615-7225

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The aim of this journal publication is to disseminate the conceptual thoughts or ideas and research results that have be...

PERHATIAN!!!

WASPADA PENIPUAN

PORTAL DEPAN WEBSITE E-JOURNAL

- **Header Jurnal:** header jurnal harus menunjukkan ciri khas jurnal tersebut, ukuran, warna dan jenis font nama jurnal di header harus sama dengan yang ada di Cover jurnal. Header juga harus mencantumkan nomor e-ISSN dan/atau p-ISSN. → **Skor maks.: 1**
- **Deskripsi Jurnal dan Nama Penerbit:** harus tercantum di halaman depan portal e-journal termasuk jenis jurnalnya (nasional atau internasional). Boleh juga mencantumkan skop utama jurnal. Boleh juga mencantumkan screenshot cover jurnal (image kecil) di halaman muka.

PORTAL DEPAN WEBSITE E-JOURNAL

- **Nama Jurnal:** Nama jurnal (“Nama Terbitan”) harus sesuai dengan yang terdaftar di ISSN (PDII LIPI); Nama Jurnal harus sesuai dengan jenis media publikasinya, e-issn atau p-issn;
- Cek nama jurnal di ISSN PDII LIPI:
<http://issn.pdii.lipi.go.id>
- Di **Open Journal System**, setting nama jurnal ada di “Journal Management” → “Setup” → “Step 1” → Journal Name.
- **Journal Name Abbreviation** adalah bukan singkatan huruf, tetapi singkatan nama jurnal yang standar internasional. Contoh: “*J. Chem. Eng.*”

Home > Volume 3 Number 3 December 2017

Journal of Educational Science and Technology (EST)

Journal of Educational Science and Technology (EST) is International Journal a peer-reviewed scientific open access, with e-ISSN : **2477-3840** and p-ISSN **2460-1497** published by Graduate Program of Universitas Negeri Makassar

EST published research articles on Education, mainly related to teaching, learning, theories and practices in education, Education Policy, Curriculum and Materials Development, Teacher Education, Technology and Media of Teaching, and other relevant activities. Before submission, please ensure the articles refer to the template and author guidelines. Any papers not fulfilling the requirements based on the guidelines to authors will not be processed.

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JURNAL PENDIDIKAN EKONOMI & BISNIS

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Current Issue

Vol 6 No 1 (2018): Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi & Bisnis

Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi & Bisnis [ISSN: 2302-2663 (Online)] is published by Faculty of Economics, State University of Jakarta. Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi & Bisnis, an electronic journal, provides a forum for publishing the original research articles, review articles from contributors, and the novel technology news related to economics education and business. This journal encompasses original research articles, review articles, and short communications, including: (1) Economics Education; (2) Business; (3) Entrepreneurship, and (4) Education Management.

Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi & Bisnis is issued two times annually, i.e. March and October. The number of articles is 20 articles per year. Every article that is sent to the Editor, will be reviewed and scrutinized by the editorial board for eligibility or publication without diminishing the substance of the article.

Kompleks Universitas Negeri Jakarta Kampus A. Gd. R, Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Negeri Jakarta,

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SUBMISSION

PORTAL DEPAN WEBSITE E-JOURNAL

- **Tampilkan Indikator Capaian Jurnal:** indikator capaian jurnal baik juga ditampilkan di bagian depan portal, misalnya: jumlah sitasi, SJR, SNIP, IPP, IF, dan/atau h-index (Google Scholar atau lainnya), terindeks di pengindeks mana saja (yang unggulan saja). Tidak perlu mencantumkan semua logo-logo pengindeks di halaman depan, jika ingin, yang unggulan saja
- **Bagian Footer:** Tampilkan Statistik Pengunjung Unik, boleh juga logo dan institusi publisher, © Copyright, dan dapat juga Badge Jenis Open Access License (Creative Commons, <http://creativecommons.org>). →

Skor maks.: 4

Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Konseling

Jurnal Kajian Psikologi Pendidikan dan Bimbingan Konseling

ISSN: 2477-2518 (Online)
ISSN: 2443-2202 (Print)

JPPK

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Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Konseling: Jurnal Kajian Psikologi Pendidikan dan Bimbingan Konseling

Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Konseling (Journal of Educational Psychology and Counseling) is a peer-reviewed scientific open access, with e-ISSN : 2477-2518 and p-ISSN 2443-2202 published by Counseling Guidance Study Program, Graduate Program of Universitas Negeri Makassar in 2015. In early 2016 Counseling and Educational Psychology Journal has built cooperation with Indonesian Guidance and Counseling Association Organization of South Sulawesi (MoU ABKIN Sul-Sel-JPPK).

Counseling and Educational Psychology Journal is an-Opened Access journal and published twice a year every June and December. It publishes the research (no longer than 5 years after the draft proposed) in term of Counseling guidance and Educational Psychology: career development, counseling techniques, media and technology counseling, career counseling, personal areas of social, behavioristic, cognitive, conceptual or empirical contributions on methodological issues in counseling psychology research.

JPPK Journal Vol.3 No 1 will be Published on June 2017 .Submit your article immediately

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JOURNAL OF EDUCATIONAL SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

ISSN : 2477-3840 (Online)
ISSN : 2460-1497 (Print)

EST

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Journal of Educational Science and Technology (EST)

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		b. Tidak berciri khas	0

MENU UTAMA WEBSITE E-JOURNAL

- **Berikan Shortcut di Menu Utama (Top Menu) portal e-journal:** bagian-bagian penting yang perlu shortcut di top menu, misalnya: *Focus and Scope; Author Guidelines and Online Submission; Editorial Board/Team; Indexing; Archives; Register*
- **Bagian Side Menu/Menu Samping:** boleh menampilkan hal-hal penting yang perlu ditonjolkan di halaman depan portal, bisa dalam bentuk images yang jika diklik akan menuju ke halaman websitenya.

BAGIAN PENTING DI “**ABOUT JOURNAL**”

- **Contact:** berisi alamat lengkap fisik kantor jurnal atau publisher jurnal atau sekretariat
- **Editorial Team:** silakan diisi Tim Pengelola jurnal (bukan Mitra Bebestari) melalui “MastHead” di Journal Management
- **Focus and Scope:** silakan diisi fokus dan skop jurnal, jangan terlalu umum, dan jangan pula terlalu rinci, namun harus dirinci.
- **Peer Review Process/Policy:** silakan diisi proses alir manuskrip mulai dari submit, proses review, hingga acceptance manuskrip termasuk jumlah reviewer per paper, dan keputusan akhir naskah. Nyatakan juga proses pemeriksaan unsur plagiarasi yang dilakukan.

Menampilkan ISSN di Homepage di OJS 2

- ▶ Via journal description, footer, atau sidebar

Via Journal Description	Via Footer	Via Sidebar
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Setup > Setup 5.2 > Journal Description• Ketik nomor ISSN• Sematkan link menuju ke database PDII LIPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Journal Manager > Setup > Setup 5.4 (Footer)• Ketik nomor ISSN• Sematkan link menuju ke database PDII LIPI	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Journal Manager > System Plugin > Generic Plugin• Custom Block Manager > Setting > Add Block• Journal Manager > System Plugin > Block Plugin• Temukan block yg baru dibuat > Edit konten• Ketik nomor ISSN• Sematkan link menuju ke database PDII LIPI• Setup 5.6 > Atu block

Journal Description di homepage

- ▶ Setup 5.2: Journal Homepage Content
- ▶ Tampilkan nomor ISSN pada Journal Description
- ▶ Sematkan link menggunakan tombol edit/insert link

Home > User > Journal Management > Journal Setup

Journal Setup

Five Steps to a Journal Website

1. Details
Name of journal, ISSN, etc.
2. Policies
Focus, peer review, sections, etc.
3. Submissions
Author guidelines, copyediting, etc.
4. Management
Access and security, scheduling, announcements, copyediting, layout, and proofreading.
5. The Look
Homepage header, content, journal header, footer, navigation bar, and style sheet.

5.2 Journal Homepage Content

By default, the homepage consists of navigation links. Additional homepage content can be appended by using one or all of the following options, which will appear in the order shown. Note that the current issue is always accessible through the Current link in the navigation bar.

Journal Description

Add a brief 20-25 word description in text/HTML which will appear just below the navigation bar.

Welcome to the Journal of Open Journal Systems!

PKP Insert/Edit Link - Google C...
Not secure | mevjournal.com/lib/pkp/lib/t...
Insert/Edit Link
Link URL:
Target:
Title:
Update Cancel

Tombol edit/insert link

Journal Page Footer

► Setup 5.4: Journal Page Footer

Home > User > Journal Management > **Journal Setup**

Journal Setup

Five Steps to a Journal Website

1. Details
Name of journal, ISSN, etc.
2. Policies
Focus, peer review, sections, etc.
3. Submissions
Author guidelines, copyediting, etc.
4. Management
Access and security, scheduling, announcements, copyediting, layout, and proofreading.
5. The Look
Homepage header, content, journal header, footer, navigation bar, and style sheet.

5.4 Journal Page Footer

This is the footer of your journal. To change or update the footer, paste the HTML code in the textbox below the navigation bar, a counter, etc. This footer will appear on every page.

Abstracted/Indexed by:

PKP Insert/Edit Link - Google C...
Not secure | mevjournal.com/lib/pkp/lib/t...
Insert/Edit Link
Link URL:
Target:
Title:
Update Cancel

Tombol edit/insert link

Plugin Management **Blok di Sidebar**

This page allows the Journal Manager to review and potentially con categories, according to their function. The categories are listed be

- Metadata Plugins
- Authorization P
- Block Plugins
- Citation Format Plugins
- Citation Database Connector Plugi
- Citation Output Plugins
- Citation Extraction Plr
- Gateway Plugins
- Generic Plugins
- Implicit Authentication Plugins
- Import/Export Plugins
- OAI Metadata Format Plugins
- Payment Plugins
- Public Identifier Plugins
- Report Plugins
- Theme Plugins
- **Install A New Plugin**

Generic Plugins

Generic plugins are used to extend Open Journal Sys

- Custom Block Manager

This Plugin lets you manage custom sidebar blo
[SETTINGS](#) [DISABLE](#) [UPGRADE PLUGIN](#) [DELETE PLUG](#)

Custom Block Manager

You can use this plugin to add or delete custom block plugins. You can then Plugin section). To place your plugin in the desired location in the sidebar, g

BLOCK NAME	ACTION
Menu	Delete
Counter	Delete
Template	Delete

Block Plugins

Block Plugins are pluggable UI compone

- Menu (Custom Block Plugin)

This is a user-generated block.
[DISABLE](#) [EDIT](#)

5.6 Journal Layout

Choose a journal theme and select layout components here. A journal stylesheet may also be uploaded, which can be used to override style data in the system-wide stylesheets and theme stylesheet (if a theme is chosen).

Journal Theme:

Journal style sheet: No file chosen

File Name: [CLASSX.CSS 2016-05-30 02:05 AM](#)

Left Sidebar

Unselected

Right

- "Developed By" Block
- Language Toggle Block
- Font Size Block
- Donation Block
- Menu (Custom Block Plugin)
- Citation Analysis (Custom Block
- Author biography Block
- Reading Tools Block
- User Block
- "Notification" Block
- Side Banner (Custom Block Plugi
- Template (Custom Block Plugin)

Menjelaskan Isi, Informasi Jelas dan Kualitas Jurnal

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For Author

For Librarians

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- Privacy Statement

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- About this Publishing System
- Statistics

Subunsur	Indikator	Nilai
Pelibatan Mitra Bestari	Melibatkan mitra bestari berkualifikasi internasional >50% dari berbagai institusi	5
	Melibatkan mitra bestari berkualifikasi nasional >50% dari berbagai institusi	3
	Melibatkan mitra bestari setempat	1
	Tidak melibatkan mitra bestari	0
Kualifikasi dewan penyunting	Lebih dari 50% penyunting pernah menulis artikel di jurnal ilmiah Internasional	3
	Kurang dari 50% penyunting pernah menulis artikel di jurnal ilmiah Internasional	2
	Lainnya (belum berpengalaman menulis artikel di jurnal ilmiah internasional)	1

Editor dan Mitra Bebestari

- Jika tidak ada URL link, maka dianggap **tidak mempunyai** rekam jejak publikasi ilmiah.
- Pisahkan Editor dan reviewer
- 5-10 orang dengan diversity yg cukup

8 poin

MITRA BEBESTARI DAN DEWAN EDITOR

- **Mitra Bebestari** (maks nilai = 5) dan **Dewan Editor** (maks nilai = 3) dinilai berdasarkan **Rekam Jejak Publikasi Ilmiahnya**
- **Strategi**: Aturlah/bagilah personil-personil yang mempunyai rekam jejak publikasi ilmiah (terutama publikasi internasional) di kedua posisi tsb. shg. >50% dari keseluruhan jumlah personil memiliki rekam jejak publikasi internasional, jika mungkin.
- **Pisahkan antara Dewan Editor dan Mitra Bebestari**
- **Dewan Editor** bersifat permanen atau pengelola tetap, sedangkan **Mitra Bebestari** bersifat semi permanen (bisa bertambah/berkurang sesuai kebutuhan)

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- **Dewan Redaksi** dan **Mitra Bebestari** seharusnya berasal dari beberapa institusi (nasional/internasional)
- **Editorial Team** sebaiknya tidak terlalu banyak jabatan, cukup dengan: *Ketua Penyunting, Penyunting Ahli/ Anggota Penyunting (jika ada), Dewan Penyunting, Penyunting Pelaksana (jika ada), dan/atau Administrasi/Sekretariat.*
- Istilah “Penyunting” = “Redaksi” = “Editor”
- Dewan Penyunting berbeda dan bukan Mitra Bebestari, namun Dewan Penyunting dapat pula ikut menelaah substansi naskah sebagaimana Mitra Bebestari (jika diperlukan).

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- **Curriculum Vitae Dewan Penyunting / Mitra Bebestari** sebuah jurnal disediakan secara daring dalam bentuk **URL pada profil user** (misalnya dihubungkan dengan Profil Rekam Jejak Dewan Penyunting di **Google Scholar** dan/atau **Scopus** dan/atau **Orchid ID**)
- **Jika tidak bisa menyediakan secara daring, dapat juga Curriculum Vitae dalam bentuk dokumen PDF yang didaringkan dan diinformasikan URL-nya (misal melalui Google Drive, kemudian Shared)**
- **Jika Dewan Penyunting/Mitra Bebestari tidak ditautkan ke URL CV, maka dianggap tidak mempunyai rekam jejak publikasi ilmiah.**

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- Kualifikasi Anggota Mitra Bebestari sedapat mungkin yang mempunyai **kualifikasi rekam jejak publikasi internasional >50%** (misal: total 10 mitra bebestari, berarti paling tidak 6 orang harus mempunyai publikasi internasional (3 tahun terakhir)) → **Nilai: 5**
- Jika Anggota Mitra Bebestari mempunyai **kualifikasi pengalaman publikasi nasional >50%** (misal: total 10 mitra bebestari, berarti paling tidak 6 orang harus mempunyai rekam jejak publikasi nasional (3 tahun terakhir)) → **Nilai: 3**
- Jika **mitra bebestari lokal** atau **tidak punya rekam jejak publikasi ilmiah** → **Nilai: 1**
- Jika tidak melibatkan mitra bebestari → **Nilai: 0**

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→ **Nilai: 3**
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- Jika semua anggota dewan penyunting **belum mempunyai pengalaman publikasi internasional** → **Nilai: 1**

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- ▶ Persistent Identifier
- ▶ Academic Account

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Bulletin of Chemical Reaction Engineering & Catalysis

e-ISSN: 1978-2993

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Faculty of Chemical Engineering & Natural Resources, Universiti Malaysia Pahang, 26300 Gambang, Pahang, Universiti Malaysia Pahang, Malaysia
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Kathleen Keefe Cooperman, Long Island University, United States

Lucy Bowes, Leverhulme Early Career Research Fellow, Department of Experimental Psychology, University of Oxford, England

Tharina Guse, Department of Psychology, University of Johannesburg, South Africa

Daphna Oyserman, Department of Psychology, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, California, USA

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Lucy Bowes

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Leverhulme Early Career Research Fellow, Department of Experimental Psychology, (SCOPUS ID: 27267591700), University of Oxford, England

Leverhulme Early Career Research Fellow, Department of Experimental Psychology, University of Oxford
Developmental psychopathology, resilience, epidemiology

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(Editor In Chief-Editor Board)

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DISARANKAN KETERWAKILAN WILAYAH MINIMAL 3 PROPINSI

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REVIEWER BUKAN SOAL BANYAKNYA TETAPI SOAL KERJANYA DAN REPUTASINYA

CONTOH STRUKTUR PERAN PENGGUNA DI OJS

Peran dan Fungsi Pengguna OJS

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- tampilan, konfigurasi situs

Manajemen Jurnal

- konfigurasi jurnal

Editor

- proses review.

Editor Bagian

- menentukan reviewer, kesesuaian bidang ilmu naskah

Reviewer

- review naskah, rekomendasi

Copy Editor

- tata bahasa

Editor Layout

- tata letak, galley naskah

Proofreader

- finalisasi naskah

Penulis

- submit naskah, revisi

Pembaca

- membaca, mengunduh

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Edit Profile Personil di OJS 2

► Jour

Home > User > Journal Management > Enrollment

Enrollment

All Enrolled Users

All Enrolled Users ▾ First Name

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ

- Journal Managers
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- Section Editors
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USERNAME	NAME	Country	Bio Statement (E.g., department and rank)	Working Languages	Actions
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<input type="checkbox"/> DHARMAWAN	Automation, Mechatronics Dharmawan -				EDIT LOG IN AS REMOVE DISABLE
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URL http://www.scopus.com/authid/detail

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Fax

Country Indonesia

Bio Statement (E.g., department and rank)

Working Languages

Bahasa Indonesia
 English

Save Cancel

Membuat Masthead di OJS 2

- ▶ Journal management > Masthead

The screenshot displays the OJS 2 interface for managing the masthead. The main page is titled "Masthead" and shows a list of positions: Editorial Team, Editor-in-Chief, International Editorial Board, Advisory Editor, Associate Editor, and Peer-Reviewer. A "Record" button is visible. A "Create Title" modal is open, showing a form with fields for "Title *" (containing "Mitra Bebestari"), "Type", and "Publish member email addresses". The modal also has "Save" and "Cancel" buttons. A "Membership" modal is also visible, showing a list of names: Dian Andriani, Aam Muharam, Yanuandri Putrasari, Roni Permana Saputra, Ghalya Pikra, and Tinton D. Atmaja. The "Membership" modal has "EDIT TITLE" and "MEMBERSHIP" buttons. The "Membership" modal also shows "1 - 6 of 6 Items" and an "ADD MEMBER" button. The "Membership" modal also has "EDIT" and "DELETE" buttons. The "Membership" modal also has a "MEMBERSHIP" button circled in red. The page number "55" is visible in the bottom right corner.

Home > User > Journal Management > Masthead

Masthead

Under People in About the Journal:

- OJS lists people in Editorial Team
- The Journal Manager creates titles

Record

TITLE

Editorial Team

- Editor-in-Chief
- International Editorial Board
- Advisory Editor
- Associate Editor
- Peer-Reviewer

1 - 5 of 5 Items

[CREATE POSITION TITLE](#)

Home > User > Journal Management > Masthead > **Create Title**

Create Title

Title *

Mitra Bebestari

Type

Publish member email addresses

- Have title appear under Editorial Team in People section of About the Journal (e.g. Editor)
- Have title appear as its own category under People (e.g. Editorial Board)

Save **Cancel**

Home > User > Journal Management > Masthead > Associate Editor > **Membership**

Membership

EDIT TITLE **MEMBERSHIP**

NAME

- Dian Andriani
- Aam Muharam
- Yanuandri Putrasari
- Roni Permana Saputra
- Ghalya Pikra
- Tinton D. Atmaja

1 - 6 of 6 Items

ADD MEMBER

EDIT | **MEMBERSHIP** | **DELETE** | ↑ ↓

55

Popup Mitra Bebestari dan Dewan Editor

Home > About the Journal > Editorial Team

EDITORIAL TEAM

EDITOR IN CHIEF
Prof. Dr. Estiko Rijanto, Indonesian Institute of Science

DEPUTY EDITOR
Aam Muharam, RCEPM-LIPI, Indonesia
Tinton D. Atmaja, RCEPM-LIPI, Indonesia

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REVIEWER ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Prof. Ir. Jamasri, Ph.D.
Department of Mechanical and Industrial Engineering
Jl. Grafika No. 2, Yogyakarta, 55172, INDONESIA

Prof. Rosli bin Abu Bakar
Faculty of Mechanical Engineering
26600 Pekan, Pahang, MALAYSIA

Prof. Taufik
Director of Electric Power Institute
San Luis Obispo, CA 93407, UNITED STATES

Prof. Dr. Ir. Suhono H Supangkat
STEI - Institut Teknologi Bandung
Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung 40135, INDONESIA

Prof. Muhammad Nizam, S.T, M.Eng.
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Jl.Ir. Sutami 36 A,Surakarta, 57126, INDONESIA

Prof. Dr. EstikoRijanto
Research Centre for Electrical Engineering
Komp LIPI JISangkuriang, Bldg 10, Bandung 40132, INDONESIA

Prof. Tapan Kumar Saha
Electrical Engineering, The University of Queensland
St. Lucia, Qld-4072, AUSTRALIA

Prof. Dr. Ir. ZainalAbidin
Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering
Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung 40135, INDONESIA

Prof. Dr. BambangRiyanto
School of Electrical Engineering and Informatics, Bandung Institute of Technology
Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung 40135, INDONESIA

PROF. ROSLI A. BAKAR

Prof. Rosli A. Bakar
<http://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.url?authorId=23092797800>
Universiti Malaysia Pahang, Malaysia

Scopus ID: 23092797800
h-index: 8

Close

PROF. TAPAN K. SAHA

Prof. Tapan K. Saha
<http://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.url?authorId=35570365800>
University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia

Scopus ID: 35570365800
h-index: 19

Close

Menampilkan list Editor di OJS 3

- ▶ Setting > Journal > Masthead > Editorial Team (Mashead)
- ▶ Pastikan semua personel sudah mempunyai link

Editorial Team
List editors, managing directors, and other individuals associated with the journal.

Editorial Team:

Editor in Chief

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Nulla cursus eros e faucibus orci luctus et ultrices posuere cubilia Curae; Etiam eu interdum ni Curabitur molestie vel metus ut dictum. Nam bibendum porta urna, ut tris sodales lorem porta nec. Nulla efficitur tristique mauris blandit ornare. Do fringilla. Pellentesque nec purus tincidunt. sodales sem at. fringilla nisi. Cra

Insert link

Url:

Text to display:

Title:

Target:

Ok Cancel

Tombol edit/insert link

List Reviewer via Static Page

- ▶ Setting > Website > Static page plugin > Add Static page
 - ▶ Isikan konten (nama, afiliasi, dan negara)
 - ▶ Pastikan semua reviewer mempunyai url link

The screenshot shows the 'Website Settings' interface with the 'Plugins' tab selected. An 'Insert link' dialog box is open, containing the following fields:

- Uri:
- Text to display:
- Title:
- Target:

Buttons for 'Ok' and 'Cancel' are visible at the bottom right of the dialog.

Tombol edit/insert link

The screenshot shows the 'Edit' page for a static page. The page title is 'reviewers' and the title is 'Reviewers'. The path is 'https://biota.ac.id/index.php/jb/%PATH%'. The content area contains a list of reviewers with their names and Scopus IDs, each preceded by a blue link icon. A blue arrow points from the 'Insert link' dialog box to the link icon in the content area.

Content:

- [I Made Putrawan](#), Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Prov. Jakarta, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 56672834000](#))
- [Dodi Safari](#), Ekikman Institute for Molecular Biology, Prov. Jakarta, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 23493586700](#))
- [Dwi Anita Suryandari](#), Universitas Indonesia, Prov. Jakarta, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 6505763338](#))
- [Mieke Marsyah](#), Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Prov. Jakarta, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 57200043826](#))
- [Sri Bahayu](#), Universitas Negeri Jakarta, Prov. Jakarta, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 57200105180](#))
- [Sorta Basar Ida Simanjuntak](#), Universitas Jenderal Soedirman, Prov. Jawa Tengah, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 57199302544](#))
- [Daniel Dioko Wahyono](#), Universitas Jenderal Soedirman, Prov. Jawa Tengah, Indonesia ([Scopus ID: 57199302544](#))

List Reviewer via Menu Items

- ▶ Setting > Website > Navigation Menus
- ▶ Add item > Choose type: Custom page
 - ▶ Isikan konten

Add item

Title *
Reviewer Acknowledgement

Create a custom page on your site and link to it from a navigation menu.
Custom Page
Create a custom page on your site and link to it from a navigation menu.

Path *
reviewer

This page will be accessible at:
<https://ojs2.e-journal.iid/2018/mev3/index.php/mev/%PATH%>
...where %PATH% is the path entered above. **Note:** No two pages can have the same path. Using paths that are built into the system may cause you to lose access to important functions.

Content

Peer-Reviewer

- Prof. István Patkó, Óbuda University, Budapest, Hungary
- Prof. Dr. Murat Lüy, Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Kirikkale University, Turkey
- Prof. Jamasri Jamasri, Gadjah Mada University, Indonesia
- Prof. Juan Carlos Alvarez, Dept. Electrical Engineering, University of Oviedo, Spain

Save Preview

Add item

Title *

Navigation Menu Type
Choose a type...
Select a Navigation Menu Type or Custom to make your own *

Save

Insert link

Url
<https://www.scopus.com/authid/detail.uri?authorId=53>

Text to display
Prof. Dr. Estiko Rijanto

Title

Target
New window

Ok Cancel

Tombol edit/insert link

view Site admin

Help

Add Menu

ation, Logout

ncements,

Add item

Indikator	Nilai
a. Organisasi profesi ilmiah	4
b. Organisasi profesi ilmiah bekerjasama dengan perguruan tinggi dan/atau lembaga penelitian dan pengembangan/ Kementerian/Non Kementerian	3
c. Perguruan tinggi, lembaga penelitian dan pengembangan	2
d. Badan penerbitan non pemerintah atau perguruan tinggi yang mendelegasikan ke sub kelembagaan di bawahnya	1
e. Penerbit selain a, b, c dan d	0

Indikator	Nilai
Organisasi profesi ilmiah	4
Organisasi profesi ilmiah bekerjasama dengan perguruan tinggi dan/atau lembaga penelitian dan pengembangan/ Kementerian/Non Kementerian	3
Perguruan tinggi, lembaga penelitian dan pengembangan	2
Penerbit selain a, b, c dan d	1

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Nama lembaga penerbit ditulis jelas di deskripsi jurnal di halaman *home*

Kerjasama dengan organisasi profesi tingkat pusat, bukan cabang dan bukan LSM

Kerjasama dalam level LPPM, bukan tingkat Fakultas/jurusan

Menampilkan Penerbit di homepage

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- ▶ Untuk penerbitan yg bekerjasama dengan Organisasi X, Sebutkan secara jelas dan sematkan link
 - ▶ Link menuju dokumen MoU
 - ▶ Link menuju website Organisasi X
 - ▶ Kerjasama dilakukan dengan Organisasi X level pusat
 - ▶ Kerjasama dilakukan di level universitas/LPPM
- ▶ Perhatikan menu Contact
 - ▶ Alamat dan kelembagaan penerbit harus riil dan bisa ditemukan
 - ▶ Lengkap dengan kodepos dan atau nomor extensi telp
 - ▶ Kesulitan korespondensi akan menyebabkan jurnal terkesan abal2

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Department of Biology

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Bogor Agricultural University

Darmaga Campus, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

Phone/Fax: +62-251-8421258;

E-mail: hayati_j_biosci@cbn.net.id

URL : <http://journal.ipb.ac.id/index.php/hayati>

Principal Contact

Dr. Berry Juliandi

Editor in Chief

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Department of Biology

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Bogor Agricultural University

Darmaga Campus, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

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Department of Biology

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Bogor Agricultural University

Darmaga Campus, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

Phone/Fax: +62-251-8421258;

E-mail: hayati_j_biosci@cbn.net.id

URL : <http://journal.ipb.ac.id/index.php/hayati>

Principal Contact

Dr. Berry Juliandi

Editor in Chief

HAYATI Journal of Biosciences

Department of Biology

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences

Bogor Agricultural University

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Jurnal Psikologi Pendidikan dan Konseling (Journal of Educational Psychology and Counseling) is a peer-reviewed scientific open access, with e-ISSN : 2477-2518 and p-ISSN 2443-2202 published by Counseling Guidance Study Program, Graduate Program of Universitas Negeri Makassar in 2015. In early 2016 Counseling and Educational Psychology Journal has built cooperation with Indonesian Guidance and Counseling Association Organization of South Sulawesi (MoU ABKIN Sul-Sel-JPPK).

Counseling and Educational Psychology Journal is an-Opened Access journal and published twice a year every June and December. It publishes the research (no longer than 5 years after the draft proposed) in term of Counseling guidance and Educational Psychology: career development, counseling techniques, media and technology counseling, career counseling, personal areas of social, behavioristic, cognitive, conceptual or empirical contributions on methodological issues in counseling psychology research.

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Upaya bimbingan belajar meliputi pengembangan berbagai aspek tersebut secara maksimal untuk mencapai prestasi belajar yang tinggi, selain itu mencegah kemungkinan hambatan yang terjadi agar peserta didik dapat mewujudkan diri sepenuhnya dalam proses

...untuk secara khusus mengembangkan suatu model layanan bimbingan belajar untuk meningkatkan motivasi berprestasi. Layanan pembelajaran diberikan kepada siswa agar dapat membantu siswa mengembangkan kebiasaan belajar yang baik untuk mengenal pengetahuan dan keterampilan serta menyiapkan diri untuk melanjutkan pendidikan pada tingkat yang lebih tinggi. Disamping itu sepanjang pengetahuan penulis di SMP Negeri 1 Enrekang belum pernah diadakan penelitian tentang hal tersebut.

Dari hasil analisis kebutuhan yang dilakukan, maka perlu adanya upaya dalam menangani rendahnya motivasi berprestasi siswa di SMP Negeri 1 Enrekang dengan cara memberikan model bimbingan belajar kepada siswa. Pemberian model bimbingan belajar karena kurangnya kemampuan individu untuk mencapai kemampuannya secara maksimal dalam mengarahkan manfaat yang sebesar-besarnya baik pada dirinya maupun pada orang lain. Pemberian model bimbingan belajar paling efektif diberikan kepada siswa karena tidak mengganggu proses pembelajaran dan materi yang diberikan sesuai dengan yang dibutuhkan oleh siswa. Bimbingan belajar dilaksanakan

Comment [BR7]: Gambarkan seperti apa model analisis kebutuhan yang dilakukan secara ringkas.

Comment [BR5]: sosial

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5	<u>Rancangan penelitian sesuai dengan tujuan</u>	√		Ada perbaikan pada artikel
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7	<u>Diagram, gambar, dan tabel cukup jelas dan fungsional</u>		√	
8	Pembahasan sesuai dengan ruang lingkup penelitian		√	
9	Hasil penelitian dibandingkan dengan teori dan temuan penelitian yang relevan		√	Ada perbaikan

PERBEDAAN MOTIVASI DAN HASIL BELAJAR BIOLOGI YANG DIBELAJARKAN MENGGUNAKAN MODEL PEMBELAJARAN INKUIRI TERBIMBING DENGAN MODEL PEMBELAJARAN LANGSUNG PADA PESERTA DIDIK KELAS X SMA NEGERI 7 BULUKUMBA

Tujuan umum penelitian ini adalah (1) Untuk mengetahui perbedaan motivasi belajar peserta didik yang dibelajarkan menggunakan model pembelajaran inkuiri terbimbing dengan motivasi belajar peserta didik yang dibelajarkan dengan menggunakan model pembelajaran langsung, dan (2) Untuk mengetahui perbedaan hasil belajar peserta didik yang dibelajarkan menggunakan model pembelajaran inkuiri terbimbing dengan hasil belajar peserta didik yang dibelajarkan dengan menggunakan model pembelajaran langsung. Penelitian ini adalah penelitian *Quasy Eksperimen*. Jenis eksperimen adalah *Posttest-Only Control Group Designs*. Populasi penelitian ini adalah kelas X SMA Negeri 7 Bulukumba sebanyak 193 orang, dan sampel terpilih sebanyak 2 kelas yaitu kelas X₂ sebanyak 25 orang dan kelas X₇ sebanyak 27 orang dengan menggunakan teknik *simple random sampling*. Instrumen yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah angket motivasi belajar dan tes hasil belajar. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa (1) Motivasi belajar peserta didik kelas yang dibelajarkan menggunakan model pembelajaran inkuiri terbimbing dan model pembelajaran langsung berada pada kategori sedang, (2) Hasil belajar peserta didik pada kelas inkuiri terbimbing berada pada kategori tinggi, dan hasil belajar peserta didik pada kelas pembelajaran langsung berada pada kategori sedang.

Comment [h1]: Materinya APA?

Comment [h2]: Judul sepertinya tidak baku dan terlalu panjang

Comment [h3]: Sampaikan saja diabstrak sampel dan lokasi penelitian

Comment [h4]: Apakah sampel dianggap cukup jika hanya 25 orang per group/kelompok???

Comment [h5]: Berapa nilai reliabilitasnya? Sudah diuji belum?? Minimal 0,6 nilai alpha cronbach

Comment [h6]: Sudah dilihat reliabilitasnya belum? Riasanya minimal

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²Instansi, alamat

ABSTRAK

Abstrak merupakan intisari dari tulisan yang menceritakan secara singkat tentang latar belakang, tujuan, metode, hasil, dan kesimpulan. Untuk naskah dalam bahasa

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Visualizing and interacting with large-volume biodiversity data using client-server web-mapping applications: The design and implementation of antmaps.org

Julia Janicki ^a, Nitish Narula ^a, Matt Ziegler ^a, Benoit Guénard ^{a,b}, Evan P. Economo ^{a,*}

^a Obihiro University of Science and Technology Graduate University, Dept. Obihiro 984-0005, Japan
^b The University of Hong Kong, School of Biological Sciences, Eukaryotic Biological Sciences Building, Pok Fu Lam Road, Hong Kong, 986, China

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DTG

ABSTRACT

The use of information has presented new opportunities for analyzing, visualizing, and interacting with data across the sciences, and biodiversity science is no exception. Recently, comprehensive datasets on the geographic distributions of species have been assembled that represent a thorough accounting of a given taxonomic group of species (e.g. birds, mammals, etc.), and which form critical tools for both basic biology and conservation. However, these databases present several challenges for visualization, interaction, and participation for users across a broad range of scientists and the public. In support of the development of a new comprehensive ant biodiversity database containing over 1.7 million records, we developed a new client-server web-mapping application, *antmaps.org*, to visualize and interact with the geographic distributions of all 13,050 ant species and aggregate patterns of their diversity and biogeography. Our application development approach was based on user-centered design principles of usability engineering, human-computer interaction, and cartography. The resulting application is highly focused on providing efficient and intuitive access to geographic biodiversity data using a client-server interaction that allows users to query and retrieve data on the fly. This is achieved with a backend solution to efficiently work with large volumes of geospatial data. The usability and utility of the final version of the application was measured based on effectiveness, efficiency, and user satisfaction, and assessed using questionnaires, usability lab studies and surveys. While the development of *antmaps.org* was motivated by a particular ant biodiversity dataset, the basic framework, design, and functionality are not specific to ants and could be used to interact with biodiversity data of any taxonomic group.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Background

The information revolution has ushered biology into an era of big data, presenting new challenges and opportunities for data-driven research (Hewes et al., 2008; Kelling et al., 2009; Keichman et al., 2011; Marx, 2013; Aze et al., 2014). Studies and initiatives that utilize technologies for data integration, analysis and communication have increased exponentially within the biological and ecological fields (Corzales et al., 2009; Patten, 2009; Perceira et al., 2011; Graham and Kennedy, 2014). Biodiversity science, as the study of life's variations, is an inherently information-rich enterprise and is currently undergoing a rapid transformation due to the aggregation and synthesis of large databases and various methods for interacting with and visualizing datasets (Corzales and Hill, 2009). Biodiversity information comes in many forms, from physical specimens to genomic sequences to field observations. While some new sources of data, such as DNA sequences, have emerged due to technological innovation, much of the recent advances relate to the digitization and consolidation of vast amounts of existing information. Much of this information that has accumulated over the last few hundred years is distributed in countless museum collections and in (sometimes difficult-to-access) published literature (Graham et al., 2004). Recent efforts to aggregate, process, and utilize biodiversity information have presented new challenges and opportunities for the field (Corzales et al., 2006, 2007; Corzales and Hill, 2009; Goodwin et al., 2015).

The importance of consolidation and digitization is especially true for a key data type in biodiversity science: records of where each species occurs (or has occurred) on Earth. In the aggregate, such data gives us a map of life on Earth and patterns relevant both for our understanding of basic biology and for designing effective conservation efforts. For example, the aggregation of species occurrence records in order to see overall patterns plays a pivotal role in inferring ecological and evolutionary processes (Jetz

^{*} Corresponding author.
E-mail address: evan@economo@obu.ac.jp (E.P. Economo).

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Afiliasi Penulis

Abstrak

et al., 2012). While these datasets are nowhere near complete for most groups of organisms (Meyer et al., 2015), the consolidation of large biodiversity datasets in vertebrates and plants has already led to insights into the global ecology and evolution of biodiversity (Schipper et al., 2008; Orme et al., 2005; Kier et al., 2005; Kraft and Jetz, 2007; Buckley and Jetz, 2007), as well as served as a critical guide to global conservation efforts (Joppa, 2015; Pimm et al., 2014).

While methods for consolidating and curating such biodiversity data are an important and active research area, we focus here on the problem of visualizing and interacting with the data through the web after a dataset is created. Our interest is driven by needs that have arisen during the recent construction of a new database on global ant biodiversity, the Global Ant Biodiversity Informatics (GABI) database (Guénard et al. in preparation). In this contribution, we report on the design and implementation of antmaps.org, a new web-mapping application focused on biodiversity data. We first discuss the database and problem that motivates this new tool as well as how it relates to existing tools.

1.2. The GABI database

Comprehensive biodiversity datasets exist for birds (eBird, 2012), mammals (Wilson and Reeder's Mammals species of the world's, 2005), amphibians (AmphibiaWeb, 2016), fish (Fishbase, 2015), and plants (GBIF, 2016; USDA and NRCS, 2016). However, comprehensive datasets that cover the vast majority of biodiversity–terrestrial invertebrates—remain a major hole in our knowledge and are an important need for both basic biology and conservation.

The GABI project is intended to be a first step towards addressing this knowledge gap by developing comprehensive data on one ecologically important animal group: ants. Although ant biodiversity is much less well documented than vertebrates, they are relatively well studied compared to most invertebrates due to their ecological importance and dominance in natural communities, their economic importance, and their fascinating social biology (Hölldobler and Wilson, 1990). This, combined with their moderate levels of diversity, makes them a good choice for a representative invertebrate group.

The GABI database is a combination of museum collection data, ant-species databases, and more notably, published literature. Species distribution data for over 8050 publications have been incorporated into the database thus far. The full description of the methods and results of this data compilation will be presented elsewhere in a dedicated publication (Guénard et al. in preparation), but the basic format of the data is species occurrence, species observed in a given location. As of December 2015 there are 1.7 million such records in the database, and the data is being actively used for biodiversity research (e.g. Emerson et al., 2015a, 2015b).

As collectors have only begun using latitude–longitude information relatively recently, the majority of the older data in the database do not have associated geographic coordinates. A long-term goal is to geo-reference these records to increase the resolution of the data, but as an intermediate step the GABI records are currently assigned to a system of polygons covering Earth's surface. These polygons are chosen practically to maximize data inclusion, and while locality information of older collections often do not include geographic coordinates, they can be easily assigned to political regions and (if applicable) island names. Admin 1 (state- or province-level) was used for larger countries (e.g. USA, China), while Admin 0 (country-level) was used for smaller countries (e.g. Ecuador, France). In some cases a biogeographic unit, such as an island (e.g. Borneo, New Guinea) was used even if it spanned political regions.

To summarize, the GABI data are arranged as a set of individual records where species names are associated with an area, geographic coordinates (if available), and citation information. Taxonomy is standardized and continuously maintained to keep pace with developments in systematics. Native/introduced status is recorded, and introduced ants only known from quarantine or other indoor environments are distinguished from

records of exotic establishment. In addition, the GABI participants curate the records in a continual effort to cull errors and identify dubious records.

1.3. Existing tools for visualizing biodiversity data

Data visualization has become not only a way to present results for specific studies, but also serve as exploration tools that researchers can use throughout the scientific process (Fox and Havelle, 2011). Particularly, web-mapping applications are becoming increasingly important in our daily lives as well as in scientific research (Touss, 2011; Zentgraf, 2015) as they enable such visualization of geographically referenced data through a web interface available online. They are good choices for presenting spatial datasets and play an essential role in facilitating the analysis and communication of these datasets.

Many web-mapping applications or online databases have been designed to centralize taxon- or region-specific biodiversity data (Fleming et al., 2007; Auer et al., 2011; Ferreira et al., 2011; Berges et al., 2010; Janicki et al., 2014), each with their own solutions to effectively serve the dataset and visualize it in an intuitive, useful manner that is suitable for its target users.

Auer et al. (2011) developed HechariaWeb, an interactive mapping application that visualizes a database of California's floral observation data. Its main goals are to present solutions to address large volumes of spatiotemporal point data and to make use of good cartographic design to create a flexible, usable client-side interface. The authors chose to visualize their data using graduated point symbols to represent aggregated count data as it enables the users to easily see the distribution of a species while having the background as a context, and centroids allow users to identify temporal periodicity of the data set.

Another example is the GBIF-MAPPA, a web-based GIS tool to explore biodiversity data on a global scale (Fleming et al., 2007). The tool was developed in order to effectively utilize the large amount of legacy biodiversity data served by GBIF. Many challenges had to be overcome during the development of the application, from assuring fast speed of access to handling large amount of data to building a flexible and intuitive mapping interface. The particular solution that is most relevant to antmaps.org is how they optimized the effectiveness of viewing dimensional data by allowing user selection of symbology for displaying map search results and by allowing the user to view or hide base map layers.

The Map of Life (MOL) 2010 project has provided an online application that serves as a global, collaborative interface for viewing and saving species distribution information (Jetz et al., 2012). It stores over 370 million records, visualizes species ranges and provides species lists for different geographic areas for over 950,000 species. Its main goal is to merge species distributional knowledge and it aims to improve quality control of data by means of data integration and to increase the potential of data by simplifying the process of scientific exploration and analysis. The interface includes two views, species and location, each with clear entry points for intuitive user navigation and good filtering options to effectively handle the large dataset.

Several biodiversity web resources focused on ants are available. In particular, both AntWeb.org (AntWeb, 2010) and AntWiki.org (AntWiki, 2010) are multibotered resources on ant biodiversity that include information on geographic distribution. These sites are essential tools for myrmecologists (and are used daily by the authors of this ms) and have significant value for outreach and education. But, neither currently have the capability to present all the data types included in the GABI dataset, and neither are optimized for geographic data exploration given their more generalized goals.

1.4. Objectives for antmaps.org

The motivation behind the application is to support ant biology and biodiversity research by creating a tool for researchers and other interested parties based on the GABI dataset, while drawing upon the

Judul Sirahan

Sistematika pembaban

these functions and maintain efficiency, but at present it seems to us that a set of mutually reinforcing web applications can be most efficiently utilized by a knowledgeable user. To facilitate the synergy between sites, we have made prominent links that allow the user to easily jump from a species or higher taxon map to the corresponding page in AntWeb.org or AntWiki.org.

It is also worth questioning why taxon-specific sites might be useful when generalized tools that cover all taxonomic groups are available (Fleming et al., 2007; Map of Life, 2016). While we don't have any conviction that this will remain true in the long-term, at present the taxon-specific applications facilitate more efficient interaction for researchers, and more direct control over display and curation of the data in a way that is tailored to the taxon of interest. This means that the menus are focused on the taxonomic scales that are relevant for ants, and features like the range classification (native, introduced, indoor introduced, need verification)—that may not be relevant for all taxa—can be implemented. At the same time, specialized sites like ours may be difficult to find for biologists outside the ant research community or the general public, who may casually or occasionally want to find information on ant biodiversity. The obvious advantage of a centralized website is that it is easily discoverable. Our near-term goal is to develop mechanisms that allow our data to sync with these other websites. This would suggest one long-term model for the biodiversity related web-ecosystem: a hub-and-spoke network of focused websites that are tailored to specific taxa of interest, connected to centralized, generalized websites.

Biodiversity research is as important and pressing as it ever has been, and not for positive reasons (Guénard et al., 2012). The relatively new field of biodiversity informatics is poised to muster the considerable capabilities of modern computation and data-science just when it is needed most. Here we introduced a novel tool that may assist scientists in the study of ant biodiversity by providing efficient access to comprehensive biogeographic data and to visualize and discover biotic patterns. While the antmaps.org site is tuned for our focal taxon with respect details such as the taxonomic levels of the menus, the minimalist biodiversity-mapping framework could easily be adapted for other groups. No doubt, the ecosystem of biodiversity-related web applications will continue to grow and self-organize in the coming years and decades.

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Fig. 2. The Species Range Maps View. Colors reflect different status of the species in each area (e.g. native, exotic, etc.).

Table 1
Evaluation method and respective metrics.

Evaluation method/metric	Effectiveness	Efficiency	Satisfaction
Questionnaire			X
Usability testing	X	X	X
Survey	X		X

Table 2
Usability testing scenarios and tasks, with associated goals of each task.

Scenarios and tasks	Goal of task
<p><i>Scenario 1:</i> You are a taxonomist and you collected an ant specimen in Panama, and you know it is in the genus <i>Atta</i>. You want to know what <i>Atta</i> species are found in Panama to compare the specimen you collected to these species (Task 1). You also want to see how <i>Atta</i> is distributed across the world (Task 2).</p> <p>You have identified the specimen as <i>Atta cephalotes</i>. You want to know the geographic distribution of this species (Task 3). You also want to know the total number of records for the species from Panama (Task 4).</p>	<p>Retrieve data from a specific region (overall species, a specific subfamily or a specific genus)</p> <p>Visualizing the overall ant species richness on a global scale, or the species richness of a specific subfamily or genus Visualize the range of a specific species</p>
<p><i>Scenario 2:</i> You collected some specimens of <i>Pheidole megacephala</i>, a globally distributed invasive ant species, in Taiwan. You want to check <i>Pheidole megacephala</i>'s status in Taiwan (native, exotic...) and you want to get an overall picture of the species' native range (Task 5). You want to learn more about this species since it is one of the most problematic invasive ant species. To do so you would access the external link to AntWiki for this species from within antmaps.org (Task 6). Quickly scan over the range maps one after another of the 20 <i>Pheidole</i> species that come after <i>Pheidole megacephala</i> alphabetically (Task 7). Since you are collecting in Taiwan, you want to see how the ant fauna in Taiwan is distributed across the rest of the world (Task 8). Suppose a species found in Taiwan is also found in Bolivia, you believe that there is an issue with the data since there are no other species from Taiwan that are also found in South America. You want to report the data issue to the antmaps.org administrators (Task 9). Finally, given that there are many similar species found in Myanmar and Taiwan, you would like to see the how the species in Myanmar are distributed globally, and then find the number of species in common between Taiwan and Myanmar, complete this task assuming you didn't know where Myanmar is on the map (Task 10).</p>	<p>Retrieve information on citation, number of records and type of data of a particular species from a particular region Visualize the status of a species in a particular region</p> <p>Be able to access external tools from within antmaps.org</p> <p>Compare subfamily or genus diversity or species ranges one after another Compare fauna across regions</p> <p>Report data issue</p> <p>Compare fauna of two specific regions</p>

Using Barron's ToEIC Preparation Course Package To Improve
The Listening Skill For Vocational School

Umar
Universitas Sulawesi Barat, Majene Sulawesi Barat
Email: umarahaf@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

This research aims at finding out the use of Barron's TOEIC preparation course package to improve the listening of the eleventh grade students at SMK Negeri Tinambung academic year 2010/2011. The objectives of the research were to find out whether or not the use of Barron's TOEIC preparation course package significantly improves the listening ability of the eleventh grade students at SMK Negeri Tinambung academic year 2010/2011. The research used quasi experimental research design. The samples consisted of 50 students which belonged to two groups; experimental group and control group. The research data were collected using two the listening test was given to the both groups. The research results indicated that the use of Barron's TOEIC preparation course package significantly improved the listening ability of the eleventh grade students at SMK Negeri Tinambung academic year 2010/2011. The results of posttest of both groups were improved, but the use of Barron's TOEIC preparation course package was more improved than English In Progress Business & Management for SMK Year XI: TOEIC based Activities, By Musath F. Anwar. It was proved by the result of mean score of posttest of the experimental was higher than the control group in listening (83.00 > 79.40).

Keywords: Barron's TOEIC preparation course package; improvement of the listening skill; vocational School

INTRODUCTION

Teaching materials, teaching methods, and teaching strategies of English as foreign language always need the development. The development of English teaching materials, teaching method, and teaching strategies must be relevant to the students' need. They should be formulated in the curriculum decided by the government.

Beside that, the local government should generally support to the central government to improve the achievement of the students'

subjects and especially to improve the achievement of students' English subject.

One of the researchers found that the achievement of students' English subject of senior high school and vocational school in South Sulawesi is unsatisfactory where the average grade is 5.17 for language department, 5.39 for science department, and 4.93 for social studies department. This indicates that the English teaching must be evaluated by government. So some indications should be developed are teaching materials, teaching method, and teaching strategy which relevant

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[Vol 50, No 2 \(2012\)](#)

[Vol 50, No 1 \(2012\)](#)

2011

[Vol 49, No 2 \(2011\)](#)

[Vol 49, No 1 \(2011\)](#)

2010

[Vol 48, No 2 \(2010\)](#)

[Vol 48, No 1 \(2010\)](#)

2009

[Vol 47, No 2 \(2009\)](#)

[Vol 47, No 1 \(2009\)](#)

2013

[Vol 28, No 2 \(2013\)](#)

[Vol 28, No 1 \(2013\)](#)

2012 ????

2011

[Vol 26, No 1 \(2011\)](#)

2010

[Vol 25, No 2 \(2010\)](#)

Keberkalaan (best practice)

- **Volume dan nomor terbitan** harus urut, tidak boleh melompat antar terbitan dan menggunakan angka Arab
- **Satu Volume boleh habis dalam satu tahun** atau lebih dari satu tahun (namun idealnya volume habis dalam satu tahun, ganti tahun ganti volume)
- **Dalam satu volume harus berisi minimum dua nomor terbitan**, misalnya: *Volume 1 Nomor 1 Tahun 2015 (Juni)*, *Volume 1 Nomor 2 Tahun 2015 (Desember)*
- **Nomor halaman dalam satu volume harus habis** (nomor 1 dan nomor 2 halaman berlanjut). Volume berikutnya halaman harus dimulai dari halaman satu lagi.
- Jumlah halaman minimum dalam satu volume **tidak harus 200**, yang diatur adalah jumlah artikel minimum per terbit adalah 5 artikel

Penomoran Halaman

Indikator	Nilai
a. Berurut dalam satu volume	1
b. Tiap nomor dimulai dengan halaman baru	0

Index Tiap Jilid atau Volume

Indikator	Nilai
a. Berindeks subjek dan berindeks pengarang yang terinci	1
b. Berindeks subjek saja, atau berindeks pengarang saja	0,5
c. Tidak berindeks	0

Indeks tiap jilid atau volume

Di Jurnal Cetak Indeks
Harus dibuat manual
Namun Setelah OJS
Semua otomatis

The screenshot displays the OJS (Open Journal System) interface. At the top, there is a navigation menu with links: HOME, ANNOUNCEMENTS, AUTHOR GUIDELINES, FOCUS & SCOPE, ARCHIVES, EDITORIAL TEAM, and ABOUT. A search icon and the word 'SEARCH' are also present. Below the navigation, the breadcrumb 'HOME / Search' is shown. A search input field contains the text 'sitti'. Underneath, there is an 'ADVANCED FILTERS' section with options for 'Published After', 'Published Before', and 'By Author'. A 'Search' button is located at the bottom right of the filter section. The search results area shows a single entry: 'Pengaruh Capacity Building Terhadap Kinerja SKPD Pemerintah Kota Makassar' by 'Sitti Rahmawati Arfah', dated '2018-11-05', with a page range of '115-126'. On the right side of the page, there is a sidebar with a red 'MAKE A SUBMISSION' button, a 'TEMPLATE' section, and two document icons: 'Journal Template' and 'Manual Book Registrasi dan Pengunggahan'.

HOME ANNOUNCEMENTS AUTHOR GUIDELINES FOCUS & SCOPE ARCHIVES EDITORIAL TEAM ABOUT SEARCH

HOME / Search

sitti

ADVANCED FILTERS

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Search

Pengaruh Capacity Building Terhadap Kinerja SKPD Pemerintah Kota Makassar
Sitti Rahmawati Arfah
2018-11-05

115-126

MAKE A SUBMISSION

TEMPLATE

Journal Template

Manual Book Registrasi dan Pengunggahan

KELENGKAPAN JURNAL

- ▶ WEBSITE OJS
- ▶ ISSN (P-E)
- ▶ DOI
- ▶ DESKRIPSI JURNAL
- ▶ DEWAN REDAKSI
- ▶ REVIEWER
- ▶ PANDUAN PENULISAN
- ▶ TEMPLATE
- ▶ ETIKA PUBLIKASI (COPE)
- ▶ PENGINDEX (Jika ada)

- FOCUS AND SCOPE
- INFO PEMBIAYAAN
- PEER REVIEW PROSES
- PROSES REGISTRASI DAN PENGIRIMAN ARTIKEL
- SURAT PERNYATAAN ETIKA PUBLIKASI
- STATISTIK PENGUNJUNG
- KELEMBAGAAN PENERBIT
- CONTACT & ALAMAT

TERIMA KASIH

Pendampingan Jurnal

Jika Bapak/Ibu Berminat Silahkan menghubungi kami

Ilham (085299898201)

Email: ilhambakhtiar@unm.ac.id

Editor in chief EST UNM